

Future Scope and Current Energy Situation of Wind Energy, with a Simulation of Small Wind Farm in Matrix Laboratory (MATLAB)

Tithi Mukhopadhyay

Technique Polytechnic Institute, Department of Electrical Engineering, Lecturer, India

Sayak Pal ✉

Technique Polytechnic Institute, Department of Electrical Engineering, Lecturer, India

ABSTRACT:

When the world is going through extreme energy shortage, mainly the non-renewable energies, wind energy is the hope along with solar energy, hydro energy, nuclear energy and bio mass energy to meet the energy demand. In the end of 2021, in India only, the wind capacity was 40 GWatt [8]. By the end of 2030, new 30 GWatt offshore wind capacity will be installed [8]. Wind turbines may be of various shapes and sizes. When more than one wind turbines are working together to create electrical power, they form a wind farm. The aim of this particular project is to make a simulation of a small wind farm of 4.5 MW in the simulation part of MATLAB software. Here squirrel cage induction generators are used as the electrical generators connected to the turbines. It generates power for the grid. SVC is connected to the wind turbines to control the overall reactive power. The aim is to make a MATLAB Simulink phasor model of a 4.5 MW wind farm with SVC with three fully functioning wind turbines.

Keywords: energy shortage, wind energy, wind turbines, MATLAB software, wind farm.

Suggested Citation: T. Mukhopadhyay, S. Pal, "Future Scope and Current Energy Situation of Wind Energy, with a Simulation of Small Wind Farm in Matrix Laboratory (MATLAB)," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 310-319, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).22](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).22)

INTRODUCTION

Among the renewable energies and non-conventional energies available in the world, one of the most reliable and widely used form of energy is wind. Wind energy is efficient, it helps to cover some part of the huge load requirement in a practical and economical way. For domestic use, other than commercial purpose, if the application is totally home based, small wind turbines work perfectly. Based on application, the size and specification rating of the wind turbine will change. For example, smaller turbines of 20 Watt to 500 Watt are great for small house based applications, mainly as battery chargers for vehicles and sailboats. These wind turbines are also known as micro turbines. Now, when the application changes, when we need more efficient turbines with better rating, we look for 10 kWatt turbines. These turbines mainly are used for pumping water. Usual residential houses use wind turbines from 400 Watt to 100 kWatt range. This is able to drive pretty high load.

HISTORY OF WIND TURBINES

If we study the history of wind turbines, they have been in use for thousands of years. The very first application of wind energy was using it sailing. All over the world, wind energy is considered as the main driving force for boats and ships. Many hundred years later, people learned to use it for pumping water and grinding grains. Up to around 11th century it was mainly used for food production, pumping water and forming useable ground grains. It took many more years to use wind energy and convert it into electrical energy. First large wind pumps were introduced by the Dutch, the sole purpose was to drain water from lakes and marshes, so that the place is habitable by people [1]. Americans introduced medium sized wind turbines. Along with pumping water and grinding grains,

it also was used for sawing wood in the saw mills. It was very popular for its sensible and low cost efficient operation. It was the late 1800 century, when wind turbines were used to convert wind energy to electrical energy [1].

Figure 1. Traditional Dutch Wind Turbine [2]

Figure 2. Modern Wind Turbines in Present Day [3]

CURRENT WIND ENERGY SCENARIO IN THE WORLD

In recent years due to energy crisis all over the world, the use of wind turbine has increased a lot. In 2021 only, electricity generation from wind energy has increased around 273 TWh [6].

Table 1 Wind Energy Data from 2010 to 2030 [5]

Units: TWh	
Year	Historical
0	Historical
2010	342.7
2011	437.3
2012	525.2
2013	647.3
2014	719.1
2015	839.8
2016	959.2
2017	1126.9
2018	1255.9
2019	1421
2020	1596.8

2021	1870.3
2030	7932.5 (Total)

Figure 3. Wind Power Generation from 2010 to 2030 [5]

If we go through the data from 2021, we can see, both on-shore and off-shore wind turbines were put to work to produce electricity.

Figure 4. Wind Power Capacity from 2010 to 2021 [7]

Table 2. Wind Turbine Data for Onshore and Offshore Wind [7]

Units: GW			
	Onshore wind	Offshore wind	Wind total
2010	177.6	3.2	180.8
2011	215.9	4.1	220
2012	261.3	5.4	266.7
2013	292	7.3	299.3

2014	340.4	8.6	349
2015	404.8	11.6	416.4
2016	452.9	14.2	467.1
2017	495.5	18	513.5
2018	540.9	22.2	563.1
2019	594.1	28.3	522.4
2020	701.2	34.5	735.7
2021	774.3	55.7	830

India Wind Energy Market : Primary Energy Consumption, in Exajoules, India, 2015-2021

Figure 5. Increasing Wind Energy Consumption in India from 2017-2021

WIND ENERGY IN INDIA

In India we have all three types of wind farms, i.e. onshore wind farm, near shore wind farm and offshore wind farms. Wind is very much location specific and variable energy source, to harness this power that is varying constantly is quite difficult. The Government of India along with the National Institute of Wind Energy has organized almost 800 wind monitoring stations. Wind potential maps have been published at various heights, at 50, 80, 100 and 120 meters. India's current gross wind energy potential stands at 302 GW.

Table 3. Wind Power Potential in Different States in India

SL NO	STATE	WIND POWER POTENTIAL AT 100 M (GW)	WIND POWER POTENTIAL AT 120 M (GW)
1.	Gujarat	84.43	142.56
2.	Rajasthan	18.77	127.75
3.	Maharashtra	45.39	98.21
4.	Tamil Nadu	33.79	68.75
5.	Madhya Pradesh	10.48	15.40
6.	Karnataka	55.85	124.15
7.	Andhra Pradesh	44.22	74.90
8.	Others	9.28	43.78
9.	Total	302.25	695.50

Recently in Q1 2022, India was able to add 275 MW wind energy capacity to its renewable source [9], which makes total wind energy source in India at 40.4 GW [9]. Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Gujarat and Maharashtra are still the leading states when it comes to wind to electricity conversion that is 72% of the total capacity [9].

MATRIX LABORATORY (MATLAB SIMULATION)

The objective of this simulation is to make a small wind farm of 4.5 MW in the simulation part of MATLAB software. Here squirrel cage induction generators are used as the electrical generators

connected to the turbines. It generates power for the grid. SVC is connected to the wind turbines to control the overall reactive power. The objective is to make a MATLAB simulink phasor model of a 4.5 MW wind farm with SVC with three fully functioning wind turbines, and follow the outcome of the turbines and SVC and take the readings to understand the work of the wind turbines connected to the grid. The objective is also to understand the function of the SVC and understand the result with and without SVC to see how it operates and controls the reactive power and overall help the performance of the system.

Controllers

There are various types of controllers; mostly used ones are proportional-plus-integral controllers and proportional-plus-derivative controllers. Their main intention is to reduce the error signal or make it closer to zero. The entire response of the system depends on the values of k_p , k_d and k_i , i.e. proportional gain, derivative gain constant and integral time respectively. When PI controllers are used, they try to make the error zero or closer to zero. In case of only using the PI controllers, the response becomes oscillatory. It also reduces the bandwidth of the system. For increasing the bandwidth, PD controllers are used. Their presence improves both the bandwidth and the damping. To have better and improved transient response PID controllers are used. They do not create oscillations in the response unlike the PI or PD controllers. It also improves the overall steady state response.

SVC

The SVC or static VAR controller is mainly used to control the overall reactive power of the system. The SVC part is entirely for the reactive power control. There might be moments, when there are faults in the system. If there is lagging power factor created due to the fault the SVC will operate in capacitive nature to increase the power factor. This process is called switched capacitor compensator. The exact opposite thing happens in case of leading power factor. The SVC operates in the inductive nature to reduce the effect of the fault and make the power factor normal again. This method is called switched inductor compensator. But all the industrial SVCs are switching mode compensators in nature, which means they can operate in both positive VARs and negative VARs. Current mode control of the system is preferable here. Switch mode compensating is cheaper and much more effective.

Figure 6. MATLAB SIMULINK Model of Turbine 1 Connected to the Grid with SVC

Figure 7. MATLAB SIMULINK Model of the Entire System with Three Turbines

There are three turbines producing 1.5MW active power each. There is external AC voltage supply given, as this system cannot work on stand alone. It needs external supply. SVC is connected with turbine 1. For the 2nd and 3rd turbines, there are MVAR to control the reactive power of the system. Later SVC can also be added depending on the system requirements. The SVC part is entirely for the reactive power control. There might be moments, when there are faults in the system. If there is lagging power factor created due to the fault the SVC will operate in capacitive nature to increase the power factor. The exact opposite thing happens in case of leading power factor. The SVC operates in the inductive nature to reduce the effect of the fault and make the power factor normal again.

OBSERVATIONS, RESULTS AND OUTPUT

The outputs from all the turbines are shown below. There is output of SVC; there are voltage output from each turbine, and the active power output from each turbine. The SVC part is entirely for the reactive power control. There might be moments, when there are faults in the system. If there is lagging power factor created due to the fault the SVC will operate in capacitive nature to increase the power factor. The exact opposite thing happens in case of leading power factor. The SVC operates in the inductive nature to reduce the effect of the fault and make the power factor normal again.

Figure 8. Output from the SVC

The above result shows the SVC output. The SVC part is entirely for the reactive power control. There might be moments, when there are faults in the system. If there is lagging power factor created due to the fault the SVC will operate in capacitive nature to increase the power factor. The exact opposite thing happens in case of leading power factor. The SVC operates in the inductive nature to reduce the effect of the fault and make the power factor normal again. The SVC output shows the output of positive sequence voltage and also the susceptance (B).

Figure 9. Active Power Output from Turbine 1

The above picture shows the output from the turbine 1, the active power coming out of the turbine 1. The nominal power for turbine 1 is 1.5MW, where the output from the turbine 1 is almost 1.5MW.

Figure 10. Active Power Output from Turbine 2

The above picture shows the output from the turbine 2, the active power coming out of the turbine 2. The nominal power for turbine 2 is 1.5MW, where the output from the turbine 2 is almost 1.5MW.

Figure 11. Active Power Output from Turbine 3

The above picture shows the output from the turbine 3, the active power coming out of the turbine 3. The nominal power for turbine 3 is 1.5MW, where the output from the turbine 3 is almost 1.5MW.

Figure 12. Voltage Output of Turbine 1

In case of turbine 1 the nominal voltage is 575 Volt. It is slightly oscillating due to presence of PI controllers in the SVC.

Figure 13. Voltage Output of Turbine 2

In case of turbine 2 the nominal voltage is 575 Volt. It is slightly oscillating due to presence of PI controllers in the SVC.

Figure 14. Voltage Output of Turbine 3

In case of turbine 3 the nominal voltage is 575 Volt. It is slightly oscillating due to presence of PI controllers in the SVC.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

This model shows a wind farm of 4.5 MW with wind turbines. The wind turbines are connected to squirrel cage induction generators. This model produces active and reactive power for the grid. But there was initial external voltage supply given. The active and reactive power output is satisfactory. The response is oscillatory due to the presence of PI controllers. To improve that kd must be used, i.e. the PD or proportional-plus-derivative controllers should be adjusted to the proper values.

This model in future can be done with other Artificial Intelligent methods such as fuzzy logic or neural network systems. They are mainly used so that they can improve the performance of the entire model as well as the Wind Turbine Conversion system. They make the performance better by making proper power factor control or even more accurate speed control or voltage control. The ideal characteristics behavior of artificial intelligence is the ability to rationalize while take actions and having the best possibility of achieving a precise goal. This model can be used to increase the number of turbines in this particular wind farm. Increasing the number of wind turbines will ensure producing more active and reactive power or the electrical power grid. Instead of making 4.5 MW power, it can produce much more power. Even multiple wind farms can be created that can produce power in Giga-Watt range. But in that case the control will be very much difficult as multiple turbines will need much more difficult control system.

This entire system can also run in grid fault or other fault conditions. Then the entire approach will be different in that case. When fuzzy logic will be applied, phasor model will not work. Discrete model of the Simulink should be used.

REFERENCE

1. EIA, Wind explained. History of wind power, 2023. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/wind/history-of-wind-power.php>
2. Wikipedia, Windmill, n.d. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Windmill#/media/File:KinderdijkWindmills.jpg>

3. National Geographic, Wind Energy Lab Tutorial, n.d. Available: <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/wind-energy/>
4. U.S. Department of Energy, Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy, n.d. Available: <https://www.energy.gov/eere/office-energy-efficiency-renewable-energy>
5. IEA, Wind power generation in the Net Zero Scenario, 2010-2030, IEA, Paris. Available: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/wind-power-generation-in-the-net-zero-scenario-2010-2030-2>
6. IEA, Wind Electricity, IEA, Paris, 2022. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/wind-electricity>
7. IEA, Wind power capacity in the Net Zero Scenario, 2010-2030, IEA, Paris, n.d. Available: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/wind-power-capacity-in-the-net-zero-scenario-2010-2030>
8. Mondor Intelligence, Wind Energy Market in India Size & Share Analysis - Growth Trends & Forecasts, 2024. Available: <https://www.mondorintelligence.com/industry-reports/india-wind-energy-market>
9. Mercom, India Adds 275 MW of New Wind Capacity in Q1 2022; Gujarat Leads, 2022. Available: <https://www.mercomindia.com/india-adds-wind-capacity-q1-2022>

